

Macroeconomic Variables and Stock Return: A Case of Nepal

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Abstract

The study has been carried out to identify the relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock return. It is indicated that there is a probability of macroeconomic factors influencing the stock return volatility. Therefore, the study is one of the evidence of how macroeconomic variables affecting the stock return in Nepal. The study has taken the stock index of Nepal Stock Exchange as the dependent variable and four different macroeconomic variables (i.e. Inflation rate, interest rate, gold price and exchange rate) as independent variables five years monthly data from June 2007 to July 2013 are used for the analysis and ordinary least square (OLS) method is used to capture the empirical evidences on this topic. Five regression models were formed and Durbin Watson, multicollinearity and ANOVA testing are performed on the data. The study reveals that stock return is negatively related to exchange rate, interest rate and gold price whereas it is positively related to inflation rate.

INTRODUCTION

The performance of stock exchange is an important issue in any country and it plays a vital role in global economics as well as in financial markets. As the economy develops, more resources are needed to meet the rapid expansion. Therefore, the stock market helps to channels idle resources from surplus to deficit units in the economy. According to Alile (1984), "The stock market serves as a veritable tool for the mobilization and allocation of savings among competing users, which are critical to the growth and efficiency of the economy". The mobilization of resources through the stock market, promotes economic growth by providing large and long term capital through issuing shares and stocks for the surplus units and supplies the funds to the

industries in need for the expansion of their business. In short, the efficient stock exchange can diversify the domestic funds and activates the productive investment which will ultimately flourish the economic activities in a country. Similarly, many empirical studies have proved that the development of the capital market is an essential element for economic growth, but, it is only possible if the stock market has a significant relationship with the macroeconomic variables.

According to the empirical evidence, the key macroeconomic variables and marketing information in the economy, which influence the stock market are Government policies, exchange rates, inflation, money supply, interest rate, foreign

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direct investment, law and order situation, political instability, security problems, Gross domestic product growth rate, judiciary crises, gold price and etc. However, the relationship between the variables and stock market may vary from country to country. As developed economies have fully explored the mobilization of resources through the capital market, the developing countries are yet to fully take the benefits of raising capital by the capital market due to which the evidence from the studies related to developed economies might not be similar to the developing economic. The empirical evidence from historical data has proven that when the inflation rate is higher in developing countries, the volatility of stocks is greater than compared to developed economies.

The relationship between macroeconomic variable and stock return is assumed to be contradicting. The movement of stock indices is highly sensitive to the changes in fundamentals of the economy and to the changes in expectations about future prospects. According to Momani and Alsharai (2012), "The market efficiency theory, which is considered as one of the most important theories in the finance and investment field, assumes that the investors can't fulfill the abnormal return (the difference between the real return and the expected return), because all the information are reflected on the share prices quickly, and even immediately, the share prices and the change on them are considered as one of the most important indicators that measure the extent of response of the securities to the economic changes".

According to Adjasi and Biekpe (2006), the investors and the policy makers can make a better investment decisions and can improve the county's overall perception and economic conditions through the investigation of the stock return and macroeconomic variables. Economic theory and empirical studies consider stock returns and thus, market index to be one of the best indicators of changes in economic activity. Therefore, in order to studies the relationship between macroeconomic

variables and stock return in context of Nepal four crucial economic variables (i.e. interest rate, inflation rate, exchange rate and gold price) are analyzed for the study.

Similarly, a number of studies investigate the link between macroeconomic variables and stock market. However, there is no consensus on the direction of causality among these variables, which remained a source of ambiguity. Even though majorities of studies are based on finding the impact of macroeconomic variable on the stock return of developed economy but the impact can be equally identified in developing economies like Nepal as well. Considering this matter, the impact of macroeconomic variable on the stock return of Nepal still needs lengthy analysis and more research attention. Further, the finding is not only useful for academic purpose but it is also helpful for the investors and the policy maker for taking investment decision.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The link between macroeconomic variables and stock returns has been an attractive subject for both financial and macro economists for a long period of time and from a decade's number of studies have been carried out to explore the link. However, there is no consensus on the direction of causality among these variables, which remained a source of ambiguity. But there are also studies which focus on a number of economic models and provide a framework to investigate the relationship.

Ali (2011) investigated that inflation and foreign remittance had a negative impact while industrial production index, market P/Es and growth rate of market capitalization had a positive impact on stock returns for Dhaka Stock Exchange. Asa and Ogunmuyiwa (2011) inspected the impact of macroeconomic variables on Average Share Price (ASP) for Nigeria and found the long-run relationship between macroeconomic variables and ASP. Bhattacharya and Mukherjee (2008) tested the link by applying the techniques of univariate

root tests, cointegration and the long-run Granger non-causality test recently proposed by Toda and Yamamoto (1995), tests the causal relationships between the BSE Sensitive Index and the five macroeconomic variables, viz., money supply, index of industrial production, national income, interest rate and rate of inflation using monthly data for the period 1992-93 to 2000-01. They found that (a) there is no causal linkage between stock returns and money supply, stock returns and national income and stock returns and interest rate, (b) index of industrial production leads the stock return, and (c) there exists a two-way causation between stock return and rate of inflation.

Singh, Mehta and Varsha (2011) observed the casual relationship between Taiwan Stock Return (portfolio) and macroeconomic variables, and the basic purpose of this study was to verify the assimilation and performance of market in current conditions, and it became significant for the origination of new macroeconomic policies. Kumar (2011) examined the nature of causal relationships between macroeconomic variables and stock market of India, which corresponded with the real and financial sector of the economy. The study adjudicated that Indian financial market not so good because only 2-3% Indians invested in the market. Ray and Vani (2003) employed a VAR model and an artificial neural network (ANN) to examine the linkage between the stock market movements and real economic factors in the Indian stock market using the monthly data ranging from April 1994 to March 2003. The results revealed that, interest rate, industrial production, money supply, inflation rate and exchange rate have a significant influence on equity prices, while no significant results were discovered for fiscal deficit and foreign investment in explaining the stock market movement.

Qayyum and Anwar (2011) checked the association between the monetary policy and the stock market in Pakistan, and found that a monetary policy has a positive and significant impact on the volatility of stock market. Ali et al. (2010) inspected the

causal relationship between the macroeconomic indicators and stock returns of KSE and found that there was a cointegration between the industrial production index and stock returns. They also found that there was no causal relationship between the macroeconomic indicators and stock returns in Pakistan. Hamao (1988) used Japanese data for the period January 1975 to December 1984 to practically examine the APT model considering macroeconomic state variables similar to those used in Chen, et al. (1986). These variables were industrial production, inflation, risk premium, term structure, foreign exchange, market indices, and oil prices. This study revealed that here is a significant impact of the mentioned macroeconomic variables on stock market return.

Linter (1975), Fama and Schwert (1977), Fama (1981, 1982), Geske and Roll (1983) and Caporale and Jung (1997) concluded that there is negative relationship between real stock returns and inflation in US and European stock markets. Chatrath and Ramchander (1997) and Hu and Willett (2000) provide evidence from India and (Alile, 1984) provide evidence from Pakistan that there are negative and significant relationships between the inflation rate and real stock returns. Mukherjee and Naka (1995) studied the relationship between the Japanese Stock Market and exchange rate, inflation, money supply, real economic activity, long-term government bond rate, and call money rate. This study revealed that there is a cointegration relationship existed test the dynamic relationship between six macroeconomic variables and the Japanese stock market, by employing a vector error correction to a model of seven equations. They find that a long-term equilibrium relationship exists between the Japanese stock market and the six macroeconomic variables such as exchange rate, money supply, inflation, industrial production, long-term government bond rate and call money rate.

Kandir (2008), Investigates the role of macroeconomic factors in explaining Turkish stock

returns for the period from July 1997 to June 2005. Macroeconomic variables used in this study are, growth rate of industrial production index, change in consumer price index, growth rate of narrowly defined money supply, change in exchange rate, interest rate, growth rate of international crude oil price and return on the MSCI World Equity Index. The empirical findings reveal that exchange rate, interest rate and world market return seem to affect all of the portfolio returns, while inflation rate is significant for only three of the twelve portfolios. On the other hand, industrial production, money supply and oil prices do not appear to have any significant affect on stock returns. Maysami, Lee, Howe and Hamzah (2004), examined the long term relationship between selected macroeconomic variables namely (Interest rate, Inflation, Exchange rate, money supply and Industrial Production) and stock market return in Singapore. This research revealed that (1) There is a significant positive relationship between inflation and Singapore stock return (2) There is evidence that stock returns are positively and significantly related to the level of real economic activity as proxies by the industrial production index (3) Short- and long-term interest rates have significant respectively positive and negative relations with the Singapore's stock market based on the results of the current study. (4) There is a positive correlation between money supply changes and stock returns.

Another study conducted by Maysami and Koh (2000) to examine such relationship in Singapore, this study conclude that inflation, money supply growth, changes in short- and long-term interest rate and variations in exchange rate contribute to co integrating relation with changes in Singapore's stock market levels. Islam and Watanapalachaikul (2003) investigate the relationship between stock prices and macroeconomic factors (interest rate, bonds price, foreign exchange rate, price-earnings ratio, market capitalization, and consumer price index) during 1992-2001 in Thailand. This study revealed that there is a significant long-run relationship between the macroeconomic variables

and Thailand stock market return.

Günşel and Çukur (2007), investigate the effect of five pre-specified macroeconomic variables on stock market return in UK using arbitrage pricing theory. These macroeconomic variables are interest rate, the risk premium, the exchange rate, the money supply and inflation. The results indicate that macroeconomic factors have a significant effect in the UK stock exchange market; however, each factor may affect different industry in different manner. Ihsan *et al.* (2007), explored the relationship of economic and financial variables with behavior of stock return and found that the unanticipated realizations of economic and financial variables were found to be a significant determinant of movement in stock returns.

Muhammad and Rasheed (2002), Conducted a study for South Asian countries i.e. Pakistan, India, Bangladesh and Sri Lanka, to find the impact of exchange rates on the stock returns. The study examines this relation for all the countries in long and short run fluctuations in exchange rate. The study used a monthly data for six years. The study found no relation for both long and short run between stock returns and exchange rates for India and Pakistan, also the same results were found for Bangladesh and Sri Lanka. As there is lack of relation between returns and exchange rates there is no need of using information regarding taking advantage from stock return due to fluctuation in exchange rate from one market to predict behavior in the other market. The study made recommendation for further research in this particular area by using weekly or even daily information in order to find more concrete evidence about stock returns and fluctuations in exchange rates.

Poon and Tong (2003), In their study work on economic volatility and instability of stocks returns. They measured economic volatility by ups and downs in inflation rate, growth in output and interest rate movement. They showed that movement in interest rate, inflation and deflation, and growth in output have little power of predictability to predict

stock return or instability in stock returns. They illustrated that risk premium of market increases adversely when volatility of market is high. But at the end they demonstrated evidence of movement of inflation and output growth on volatility of stock return and notify that in Philippine returns of stocks are inclined by High inflation.

Moore (1990) derived the result on the basis of empirical results from 1970 to 1988 that gold price and the stock/bond markets had a negative correlation, it means when gold prices are rising, the stock/bond markets are declining. Büyükalvarcı (2010) confirmed this finding by analyzing the effects of seven macroeconomic variables (consumer price index, money market interest rate, gold price, industrial production index, oil price, foreign exchange rate and money supply) on the Turkish Stock Exchange Market and found that gold is an alternative investment tools for Turkish investors. So as the gold price rises, Turkish investors tend to invest less in stocks, causing stock prices to fall. Therefore, there is a negative relationship between gold price and stock returns.

Another study from South Asia., Sharma & Mahendru (2010) examined the impact of Macro-Economic variables on stock prices in India and used the macroeconomic variables like change in exchange rate, foreign exchange reserves, inflation rates and gold prices. This study covers the period of January 2008 to January 2009 and results reveals that exchange rate and gold prices highly affect the stock prices. However, the study model uses 4 main macroeconomic variables namely, inflation rate, interest Rate, Exchange Rate and Gold price. In the following section, the previous research work reacted to the stock returns and each macroeconomic variable are explained in depth.

Various studies have been carried out to find out the relation between macroeconomic variables and stock price but still the finding varies from one to another. Therefore, the study proposes to identify the impact of macroeconomic variables on stock price in context of Nepal. It is an attempt to understand

whether the impact of macroeconomic variables on the stock price is similar as other economic or not.

RESEARCH METHORDOLOGY

The study analyzed the relationship between macroeconomic variables [Exchange Rate (ER), Interest Rate (IR), Consumer Price Index as inflation (CPI) and Gold Price (GP)] and stock prices of Nepal stock exchange (NSP) for the period July 2007 to June 2012. The study is based on secondary data from various sources such as:

Table 1: Sample description

S.n	Acronym	Variables	Data sources
1	NSP	Stock Return	Nepse Index is used to measure the stock return. Average monthly data published by Nepal Stock exchange Ltd is used to collect data.
2	INR	Inflation Rate	Consumer Price Index (CPI) is used to measure inflation rate. The data are collected from monthly Statistical bulletins of the Nepal Rastra Bank (NRB)
3	IR	Interest Rate	91 days Treasury Bill's interest rate published by NRB is taken as interest rate. As Treasury Bill is risk free investment so investor tends to invest on T-bill in order to secure their investment.
4	ER	Exchange Rate	Average of daily exchange rate published by NRB is used for exchange rate.
5	GP	Gold Price	Monthly Per gram gold price published by World bank is used to collect data.

The motive of this study is to trace the impact of selected macro-economic factors on stock return of Nepal. Similarly, five multiple regression analysis models have been formed being based on Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method to capture the empirical evidences on this topic. All the tests like Durban Watson, multicollinearity, ANOVA test, heteroscedasticity, are performed on this data. Likewise, correlation matrix, mean, median, standard deviation, etc were also used. SPSS 16 was used to find out the relation between dependent

variable and independent variables. Spreadsheet and word were also used to perform calculation and recording the research work where necessary.

The study is based on the daily data published by various sources and later on an average 60 months monthly data have been calculated from daily data. Similarly, the data have been analyzed using SPSS 16 and Ms excel.

The study test four explanatory variables with each respond variable separately because the composition of share prices included in each index varies. In this sense, a model is built up in line with the multiple regression analysis. With four independent variables the prediction of NSP is expressed by the following equation:

$$NSP = \beta_0 + ER\beta_1 + INR\beta_2 + GP\beta_3 + Et \quad (1)$$

$$NSP = \beta_0 + ER\beta_1 + INR\beta_2 + IR\beta_3 + Et \quad (2)$$

$$NSP = \beta_0 + ER\beta_1 + IR\beta_2 + GP\beta_3 + Et \quad (3)$$

$$NSP = \beta_0 + INR\beta_1 + IR\beta_2 + GP\beta_3 + Et \quad (4)$$

$$NSP = \beta_0 + ER\beta_1 + INR\beta_2 + GP\beta_3 + IR\beta_4 + Et \quad (5)$$

Where,

NSP = Monthly change in the Stock return

ER = Monthly change in the Exchange rate

INR = Monthly change in the Inflation Rate

GP = Monthly change in the Gold price

IR = Monthly change in the Interest Rate

Et = Error term

The results of the regressions have been analyzed by Coefficient of Correlation (R), Coefficient of Multiple Determination (R²) and Adjusted Coefficient of Determination (R² adj). In addition, the OLS draws inferences for testing hypotheses and F distribution is employed to test the null hypothesis.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

This part focuses on defining the hypothesis of the study on how the independent variables define a relation with the dependent variable. The primary

objective of the research is to determine the impact of macroeconomic variables on the stock return of Nepal whereas; the study also deals with each independent variable and determines its impact on stock return. In order to achieve the objective of the study, the following hypotheses are developed.

Hypothesis 1:

H₀: Inflation has no significant impact on the stock return of Nepal

i.e, H₀: β_i=0

H₁: There is a significant impact of inflation rate on the Stock return of Nepal.

i.e, H₀: β_i ≠ 0

Hypothesis 2:

H₀:: Interest rate has no significant impact on the stock return of Nepal

H₁: There is a significant impact of interest on the Stock return of Nepal.

Hypothesis 3:

H₀:: Exchange rate has no significant impact on the stock return of Nepal

H₁: There is a significant impact of exchange rate on the Stock return of Nepal.

Hypothesis 4:

H₀:: Gold price has no significant impact on the stock return of Nepal

H₁: There is a significant impact of gold price on the Stock return of Nepal.

Hypothesis 5:

H₀: There is no significant impact of macroeconomic variables on the Stock return of Nepal.

H₁: There is a significant impact of macroeconomic variables on the Stock return of Nepal.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data collected from the secondary sources are analyzed and discussed in this topic. The results

data are gathered and they are transformed into information with the help of SPSS 16 software and Microsoft Excel. Microsoft excel was used to present data on tables and line graph. Similarly, SPSS 16 was used to find the variances and standard deviation of the variables. Through the Multiple regressions the relationship among the variables has been identified.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistic of Study Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Stock Return	60	-14.29	21.33	-0.5497	7.61986
Exchange Rate	60	-5.854	8.767	0.49318	2.818334
Interest Rate	60	-82.832	100.733	5.73175	34.551835
Gold Price	60	-10.61	13.88	2.12183	4.269762
Inflation Rate	60	-19.544	32.417	1.83867	10.154028

Table 2 show that the average value of the change in stock return is -0.5497 and the standard deviation is 7.61986. It indicates moderate volatility of stock returns. Likewise, the mean change in the exchange rate is 0.49318 and its standard deviation is 2.818334 which indicate no significant variation in exchange rate.

Similarly, the average value and standard deviation of change in Interest rate is 5.73175 and 34.551835 respectively, which is highest among other variables and it indicates high volatility of Interest rate. Likewise, the mean change in gold price is 2.12183 and the standard deviation is 4.269762 which indicate moderate volatility. The mean of change in inflation rate is 1.83867 and the standard deviation is 10.154028 implying that there is significant variability in inflation rate.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix of Study Variables

		Stock Return	Exc. Rate	Interest Rate	Gold Price	Inflation Rate
Stock Return	Pearson Correlation	1	-.398**	-0.207	0.178	0.124
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.002	0.113	0.174	0.344
	N	60	60	60	60	60
Exchange Rate	Pearson Correlation	-.398**	1	-0.096	-0.013	0.014
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.002		0.466	0.919	0.913
	N	60	60	60	60	60
Interest Rate	Pearson Correlation	-0.207	-0.096	1	-0.043	0.195
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.113	0.466		0.745	0.136
	N	60	60	60	60	60
Gold Price	Pearson Correlation	-0.178	-0.013	-0.043	1	-0.106
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.174	0.919	0.745		0.422
	N	60	60	60	60	60
Inflation Rate	Pearson Correlation	0.124	0.014	0.195	-0.106	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.344	0.913	0.136	0.422	
	N	60	60	60	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Pearson's product movement correlation coefficient is used to test the relationship between the variables, denoted by Greek letter ρ . Its range from (+1 to -1) when ($\rho > +1$) it indicates a positive linear relationship and if ($\rho < -1$) it indicates a negative linear relationship and if ($\rho=0$) it shows no relationship among the variables. (Khan, 2013)

The correlation matrix in the table shows the correlation between stock return, inflation rate, exchange rate, gold price and interest rate. The Pearson correlation indicates the relation between variables and significance indicates the P value.

$$NSP = \beta_0 + ER\beta_1 + INR\beta_2 + IR\beta_3 + Et \quad (2)$$

Table 7: Model Summary of Second Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
2	0.5020	0.2520	0.2119	6.764	1.363
a. Predictors: (Constant), Interest.Rate, Exchange.Rate, Inflation.Rate					
b. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return					

The Adjusted of the second model is 21.19% which implies that the 21.19% of the total variability in the stock return of Nepal is explained by inflation rate, exchange rate and interest rate. Likewise, the D-W test is 1.363 which is near to 2 so there is no cross correlation of a signal with itself in the model which means there is less chances of overestimation from the model.

Table 8: Coefficients of Second Model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
2	(Constant)	0.123	0.910		0.135	0.893
	Exchange.Rate	-1.156	0.314	-0.428	-3.682	0.001
	Inflation.Rate	0.140	0.088	0.186	1.577	0.120
	Interest.Rate	-0.063	0.026	-0.284	-2.398	0.020
a. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return						

The significant value or P value of exchange rate is 0.001 which is smaller than 0.05 so, it rejects Ho. The exchange rate in the model implies that it has an impact on the stock return of Nepal. Further; the beta in unstandardized coefficients indicates that, 1% change in exchange rate decrease the stock return by 1.156 when all other independent variables are constant. Similarly, the significant value of interest rate is also less than 0.05 so it also have significant impact on stock return. However, the significant value of inflation rate is greater than 0.05 so there is no significant relationship between stock return and inflation rate. The model can be further expressed as below:

$$NSP = 0.123 + 1.156ER + 0.140INR - 0.063IR + Et \quad (2)$$

Table 9: ANOVA testing of Second Model

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
2	Regression	863.29	3	287.76	6.29	0.001
	Residual	2562.39	56	45.76		
	Total	3425.67	59			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Interest.Rate, Exchange.Rate, Inflation.Rate						
b. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return						

According to the table, the significant value from the ANOVA testing of model 1 is 0.001 which is less than level of significant (i.e. 0.05) so the reject the H_0 . It indicates that the interest rate, exchange rate and inflation rate have relationship with stock return. Further, the change in these variables has significant impact on the change in stock return.

Testing Third Model

The third model of the study includes exchange rate, interest rate and gold price as an independent variable and stock return as the dependent variable. The purpose of forming the model is to identify whether the change in independent variables impacts the change in dependent variables or not. The third model is expressed as below:

$$NSP = \beta_0 + ER\beta_1 + IN\beta_2 + GP\beta_3 + E_t \quad (3)$$

Table 10: Model Summary of Third Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
3	0.5065	0.2565	0.2167	6.7439	1.118
a. Predictors: (Constant), Gold.Price, Exchange.Rate, Interest.Rate					
b. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return					

The Adjusted is 21.67%. In addition, the gold price, exchange rate and interest rate in the model is accounted for a 21.67 % variance in stock return. Similarly, the D-W result to 1.118 which is nearer to 2 so it implies no cross correlation between data of the variables at different time lag.

Table 11: Coefficients of Third Model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
3	(Constant)	1.077	1.003		1.073	0.288
	Exchange.Rate	-1.149	0.313	-0.425	-3.671	0.001
	Interest.Rate	-0.056	0.026	-0.256	-2.208	0.031
	Gold.Price	-0.347	0.206	-0.194	-1.686	0.097
a. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return						

As for individual coefficient of macroeconomic variables in the model 3, two variables are found significant where as gold price is insignificant as expected. Further, the significant value of exchange rate is 0.001 which is less than 0.05 so the exchange rate has significant impact on the change of stock return in the model. The beta also implies that the increase in 1% of exchange rate, decrease the stock return by 1.149 when all other variables remain constant. Similarly, the significant value of interest rate is also less than 0.05 so it indicates that the interest rate has significant impact on the stock return. Further, in case of all other variable remaining constant, the increase in interest rate by 1% impact stock return to decrease by 0.056. The economic corollary is that exchange rate, interest rate and gold price have negative relation with the stock return. The model can be interpreted as below:

$$NSP = 1.077 - 1.149ER - 0.056IR - 0.347GP + Et$$

(3)

Table 12: ANOVA testing of Third Model

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
3	Regression	878.7904	3	292.9301	6.440852	0.001
	Residual	2546.882	56	45.48003		
	Total	3425.672	59			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Gold.Price, Exchange.Rate, Interest.Rate						
b. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return						

F-test is use to check whether the overall model is significance or insignificance. Since the significant value of the model 3 is less than 0.05, the model is significant. It also further implies that the independent variables have relation with dependent variable.

Testing Fourth Model

The fourth model consist of inflation rate, interest rate and gold price as an independent variables and stock return as dependent variables to study the impact of independent variables on the independent variable.

$$NSP = \beta_0 + INR\beta_1 + IR\beta_2 + GP\beta_3 + Et$$

(4)

Table 13: Model Summary of Fourth Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
4	0.316533	0.100193	0.051989	7.41914	1.557
a. Predictors: (Constant), Gold.Price, Interest.Rate, Inflation.Rate					
b. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return					

The coefficient determination is use to check whether the model is good fit or not. It's range from 0 to 1. In the above table, the value of is 0.100193, which is not near to 1. It shows that only 10% of variation in the dependent variable has explained by the independent variables. Therefore, the model is not so good fit. Similarly, the D-W test result is 1.557 which is near to 2 so it indicates that there is no autocorrelation among the variables' data within the different time lag.

Table 14: Coefficients of Fourth Model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
4	(Constant)	0.198	1.104		0.179	0.858
	Inflation.Rate	0.115	0.097	0.154	1.184	0.241
	Interest.Rate	-0.054	0.029	-0.244	-1.888	0.064
	Gold.Price	-0.307	0.228	-0.172	-1.349	0.183
a. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return						

As for the individual coefficients of macroeconomic variables are concerned, none of the variables was found significant. However, the result indicates that the stock return have positive relationship with stock return and negative relationship with interest rate and gold price. Further, the estimated regression model can be interpreted as below:-

$$NSP = 0.198 - 0.115INR - 0.054IR - 0.307GP + E_t$$

(4)

Table 15: ANOVA testing of Fourth Model

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
4	Regression	343.2	3	114.4	2.1	0.1
	Residual	3082.4	56	55.0		
	Total	3425.7	59			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Gold.Price, Interest.Rate, Inflation.Rate
 b. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return

Since, the significant value from the F test is greater than 0.05 so the overall model is insignificant which means that there is no significant relationship between dependent and independent variable. It does not reject Ho.

Testing Fifth Model

The fifth model of the study includes all the four independent variables to identify its impact of the stock return. The model is expressed as below:

$$NSP = \beta_0 + EP\beta_1 + INR\beta_2 + GP\beta_3 + IR\beta_4$$

(5)

Table 16: Model Summary of Fifth Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
5	0.532335	0.28338	0.231262	6.680915	1.26

a. Predictors: (Constant), Interest.Rate, Gold.Price, Exchange.Rate, Inflation.Rate
 b. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return

The coefficient of determinant (R) and Adjusted (Adjusted R Square) of the model is 0.28338 and 0.23126 respectively. So it indicates that only 28.33% of variation in the dependent variables has explained by the independent variables. Therefore, the model is moderately good fit. Similarly, the D-W result is 1.26 which is nearer to 2 so, it indicates no autocorrelation among the variables.

Table 17: Coefficients of Fifth Model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
5	(Constant)	0.832	1.008		0.825	0.413
	Exchange.Rate	-1.163	0.310	-0.430	-3.750	0.000
	Inflation.Rate	0.126	0.088	0.168	1.436	0.157
	Gold.Price	-0.318	0.205	-0.178	-1.552	0.126
	Interest.Rate	-0.064	0.026	0.288	-2.465	0.017

a. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return

As for the individual coefficients of macroeconomic variables are concerned, two variables i.e. exchange rate and interest rate are significant where as inflation rate and gold price is not so significant for the change of stock return. However, the coefficient table also shows that exchange rate, gold price and interest rate are negatively related to the stock return and inflation rate is only positively related to the stock return. The estimated regression model can be expressed as below:-

$$NSP = 0.832 - 1.163EP + 0.126INR - 0.318GP - 0.064IR + Et \quad (5)$$

Table 18: ANOVA testing of Fifth Model

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
5	Regression	970.77	4	242.69	5.437	0.001
	Residual	2454.90	55	44.63		
	Total	3425.67	59			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Interest.Rate, Gold.Price, Exchange.Rate, Inflation.Rate

b. Dependent Variable: Stock.Return

From the ANOVA or F test, the value of F is 5.437 and its significant value is 0.001 which is less than 0.05; it proves that all four macroeconomic variables are simultaneously affecting the change of stock return in Nepal.

Multicollinearity analysis

To test the multicollinearity among the variables, each independent variable is treated as dependent variable separately. The rule of thumb is, if the tolerance is below 0.10 or if the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is above 10 then it indicates multicollinearity problem among independent variables which influence the validity of multiple regression models. The tests are explained below:

Table 19: Multicollinearity analysis when Inflation rate is treated as dependent variable

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Exchange rate	0.798	1.252
Interest rate	0.910	1.099
Gold price	0.950	1.053
Stock return	0.743	1.345

a. Dependent Variable: Inflation rate

According to the table, the Variance inflation factors (VIF) of the model where the inflation rate is taken as dependent variable are 1.252, 1.099, 1.053 and 1.345 with the exchange rate, interest rate, gold price and stock return respectively which is less than 10 so, the analyze indicates that there is no problematic multicollinearity between the variables.

Similarly; the tolerance value of the exchange rate, interest rate, the gold price and stock return is 0.798, 0.910, 0.950 and 0.743 respectively which is more than 0.1 so according to tolerance also there is no significant problem of multicollinearity between independent variables when the inflation rate is treated as the dependent variable.

Table 20: Multicollinearity analysis when Exchange rate is treated as dependent variable

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Interest rate	0.904	1.106
Gold price	0.957	1.045
Stock return	0.900	1.111
Inflation rate	0.929	1.076

a. Dependent Variable: Exchange rate

For testing the multicollinearity, the exchange rate is treated as the dependent variable. The result of tolerance rate of interest rate, gold price, stock return and inflation rate is more than 0.10. Likewise; the VIF of all the independent variables is less than 10 so, it indicates that there is no significant multicollinearity between the variables.

Table 21: Multicollinearity analysis when Interest rate is treated as the dependent variable

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Gold price	0.954	1.048
Stock return	0.796	1.257
Inflation rate	0.973	1.027
Exchange rate	0.831	1.203

a. Dependent Variable: Interest rate

The tolerance value of gold price is 0.954, stock return is 0.796, inflation rate is 0.973 and the exchange rate is 0.831 which is more than 0.10 so, it indicates that there is no significant problem of multicollinearity among the variables.

Further, the VIF of gold price is 1.048, stock return is 1.257, inflation rate is 1.027 and exchange rate is 1.203 so all the variables have VIF less than 10 which also indicates that there is no significant problem of multicollinearity.

Table 22: Multicollinearity analysis when Gold price is treated as the dependent variable

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Stock return	0.748	1.337
Inflation rate	0.920	1.087
Exchange rate	0.797	1.255
Interest rate	0.864	1.158

a. Dependent Variable: Gold price

The tolerance value and VIF of Multicollinearity analysis when Gold price is treated as the dependent variable are more than 0.10 and less than 10 respectively which indicates that there is no significant multicollinearity.

CONCLUSIONS

In Nepal also similar relation between macroeconomic variables and stock return exists therefore, the main objective of the study is to identify the relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock return. Referring to the study carried out in developed and developing countries, it is indicated that there is a high probability of macroeconomic factors influencing the stock return volatility. Therefore, the study is on the basis of the evidence of how macroeconomic variables affecting the stock return in Nepal. For the purpose, the stock index of Nepal Stock Exchange, the only stock market of Nepal has been taken as dependent variable and four different macroeconomic variables (i.e. Inflation rate, interest rate, gold price and exchange rate) are used to find out the impact of these variables on NEPSE index. Similarly, five years monthly data from June 2007 to July 2013 are used for the analysis and ordinary least square (OLS) method is used to capture the empirical evidences on this topic. Five regression models were formed and Durbin Watson multicollinearity and ANOVA testing are performed on the data.

The finding from the Pearson correlation matrix reveals that change in the exchange rate has significant impact on the change in stock return. It also indicates that stock return and exchange rate have negative relationship which means that in case of increase in exchange rate the stock return decreases and vice versa. However, -39.8% of Pearson correlation test indicates moderate negative correlation between the two variables. Since the study has taken buy rate offered by NRB as an exchange rate so appreciation of exchange rate indicates appreciation of Nepalese currency against US Dollar. Therefore, the correlation matrix concludes that stock return is negatively correlated to Nepalese currency. Similarly, the correlation matrix also indicates the negative relation of stock return with interest rate and the Gold price with -20.7% and -17.8% respectively. Besides these three negatively correlated variables, stock return is positively correlated with inflation rate with 12.4%.

Macroeconomic Variables and Stock Return: A Case of Nepal

The five multiple regression models have been formed to identify the relationship between macroeconomic variables and also to identify which model is suitable to forecast the change in stock return. In model 1, NEPSE index has been taken as a dependent variable and exchange rate, inflation rate and gold price as an independent variable. The finding from the first model reveals that 20.4% of change in Stock return is caused by Gold price, Exchange rate and Inflation rate. From the ANOVA test it is also revealed that the model is statistically significant as its level of significant is less than 0.05. However, the coefficients table reveals that the only exchange rate among these three variables is statistically significant.

Likewise, in the second model exchange rate, inflation rate and interest rate have been taken as independent variables to measure their impact on the change in stock return. Since the R^2 of the model is 0.2520 so it indicates that the 25.2% of change in stock return is caused by these three variables. If only coefficient of the determinant is taken to measure the effectiveness of the model, then second model is more appropriate than the first model. From the ANOVA test it is also revealed that the model is significant as its significant level is less than 0.05 so it rejects H_0 .

The third model includes exchange rate, interest rate and gold price as an independent variable and stock return as the dependent variable. The coefficient of determination indicates that 25.65% of change in stock return is determined by the gold price, exchange rate and interest rate. In the model, all the independent variables are statistically significant beside gold price. Similarly, for the F test result indicates that the model is significant. So, this variable does have an impact on the change in stock return of Nepal.

The beta from unstandardized coefficients also implies that when there is a 1 % increase in exchange rate, stock return decrease by 1.149 when all other variables remain constant. Further, in case of all other variable remaining constant, the increase in interest rate by 1% impact stock return to decrease by 0.056. In case of all other variables remaining constant, when there is a 1 % increase in the gold price, stock returns decrease by 0.347. The economic corollary is that exchange rate, interest rate and gold prices have a negative relation to the stock return.

The fourth model consists of inflation rate, interest rate and gold price as an independent variable and stock return as dependent variables. The coefficient determination is used to check whether the model is a good fit or not. Since the R^2 of the model is 0.100193, which is not near to 1. It shows that only 10% of variation in the dependent variable has explained by the independent variables. Therefore, the model is not so good fit.

As the individual coefficients of macroeconomic variables are concerned, none of the variables were found significant. However, the result indicates that the stock return has a positive relationship with stock return and negative relationship with interest rate and gold price. Similarly, the overall model is also not significant as its level of significance is greater than 0.05. So, the model is so appropriate to predict impact of macroeconomic variables on stock return.

The fifth and last model includes all the four independent variables. The coefficient of determinant (R^2) and Adjusted (R^2) of the model is 0.28338 and 0.23126 respectively. So it indicates that 28.33% of variation in the dependent variables has explained by the independent variables. Therefore, the model is moderately good fit. As for the individual coefficients of macroeconomic variables are concerned, two variables, i.e. exchange rate and interest rate are significant, whereas inflation rate and the gold price is not so significant. However, the coefficient table also shows that exchange rate, gold price and interest rate are negatively related to the stock return and inflation rate is only positively related to the stock return.

The conclusion of the analysis of independent variables suggests that exchange rate, interest rate and inflation rate are negatively correlated with the stock return and only inflation rate is positively correlated to stock return. However, there is no such strong correlation amongst the independent variables.

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